

A Study on Thyroid Profile in Chronic Liver Disease Patients Admitted in a Rural Tertiary Care Hospital

Shashank Shekhar¹, Preeti Sinha², Wahengbam Purnakishor Singh³

¹Senior Resident, Department of General Medicine, Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, UP, India.

²Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesia, Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, UP, India.

³HOD, Department of Medicine, Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, UP, India.

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Preeti Sinha

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Abstract:

Background: Chronic liver disease (CLD) is a significant global health issue, with complications that extend beyond the liver, affecting other organ systems including the thyroid gland. Thyroid dysfunction is common in CLD patients and can significantly impact clinical outcomes. Despite this, thyroid function is often under-monitored in CLD management. This study aimed to analyze the thyroid profile in patients with chronic liver disease admitted to a rural tertiary care hospital and to identify the prevalence and types of thyroid dysfunction in this population.

Methods: The study included 80 patients diagnosed with CLD. Demographic data, medical history, and thyroid function tests (TSH, FT4, FT3) were collected. SPSS version 23.0 was used for the statistical analysis, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results: Of the 80 patients, 55% were euthyroid, while 45% exhibited thyroid dysfunction, including subclinical hypothyroidism (17.5%), overt hypothyroidism (10%), subclinical hyperthyroidism (12.5%), and overt hyperthyroidism (5%). A significant association was found between thyroid dysfunction and the severity of liver disease, with a higher prevalence of thyroid abnormalities in patients with more severe liver disease ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Thyroid dysfunction is prevalent among chronic liver disease patients, especially those with advanced liver disease. Regular monitoring of thyroid function in these patients is crucial for early detection and management of thyroid abnormalities.

Recommendations: Integrated care approaches including routine thyroid function tests should be implemented for chronic liver disease patients to improve clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Chronic Liver Disease, Thyroid Dysfunction, Thyroid Profile, Hypothyroidism, Hyperthyroidism.

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Introduction

The steady decline in liver function over months to years is the hallmark of chronic liver disease (CLD), a major global health concern. This includes cirrhosis, alcoholic liver disease, viral hepatitis, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), among other liver diseases. Liver illness ranks among the top ten causes of death globally, as reported by the World Health Organisation [1], highlighting the urgent need for all-encompassing therapeutic approaches. An increasing amount of studies has shown how closely liver function is related to other organ systems, especially the endocrine system, in which the thyroid gland plays a major role.

The thyroid gland secretes thyroid hormones, mainly triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4), which affect many physiological processes and control metabolism. Thyroid function changes can

have a substantial impact on general health, and systemic disorders such as CLD can also have a major impact on thyroid function. Patients with CLD may experience hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, or euthyroid sick syndrome as a result of thyroid malfunction, each of which might have different clinical consequences [2]. Different studies show varying frequencies of thyroid problems in CLD patients, indicating a complicated and nuanced link.

According to research, there are several factors contributing to the pathophysiology of thyroid dysfunction in CLD, including modifications in the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis, altered thyroid hormone metabolism, and the direct effect of liver disease severity on thyroid function [3]. As an example, the liver is essential for converting T4 to T3, and problems with liver function might result

in lower T3 levels, which can exacerbate hypothyroidism. Thyroid dysfunction can also be made worse by the oxidative stress and chronic inflammation linked to CLD, which makes the clinical care of these patients much more challenging [4].

Given the significant interplay between the liver and thyroid gland, routine monitoring of thyroid function in CLD patients is increasingly advocated. Early identification and management of thyroid dysfunction can potentially improve clinical outcomes and quality of life for these patients. However, despite growing awareness, thyroid function is often overlooked in the management of CLD, leading to underdiagnosis and undertreatment of thyroid-related complications.

This study aimed at analyzing the thyroid profile in chronic liver disease patients admitted to a rural tertiary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of February 2023 - February 2024 at Rajshree Medical Research Institute, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Participants: The study included 80 patients diagnosed with chronic liver disease.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Diagnosed with chronic liver disease.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a known history of thyroid disorders.
- Patients on medications affecting thyroid function.
- Pregnant women.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the pool of eligible patients. Data collection and analysis were conducted blinded to the participants' identities to avoid observer bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of patient interviews, medical records, and laboratory tests. The thyroid profile was assessed using blood samples to measure thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free thyroxine (FT4), and free triiodothyronine (FT3) levels.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. Demographic and clinical features were gathered using descriptive statistics. The mean \pm standard deviation was used to express continuous variables, whereas frequencies and percentages were used to express categorical variables. P-values less than 0.05 were regarded as statistically significant.

Result

The study comprised a cohort of 80 patients who had been diagnosed with chronic liver disease. Table 1 provides a summary of the demographic and clinical features of the participants.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	52.4 \pm 12.3
Gender	
Male	54 (67.5%)
Female	26 (32.5%)
Mean Duration of Liver Disease (years)	5.6 \pm 3.1
Etiology of Liver Disease	
Alcoholic Liver Disease	34 (42.5%)
Viral Hepatitis (B or C)	26 (32.5%)
Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD)	14 (17.5%)
Other	6 (7.5%)
Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	26.8 \pm 4.5
Child-Pugh Score	
A	20 (25%)
B	34 (42.5%)
C	26 (32.5%)

Thyroid function tests showed the following results (Table 2):

Table 2: Thyroid Profile Analysis

Parameter	Mean Value	Normal Range
TSH (mIU/L)	3.5 \pm 2.2	0.4 - 4.0
FT4 (pmol/L)	11.5 \pm 4.6	9.0 - 20.0
FT3 (pmol/L)	4.1 \pm 1.3	3.5 - 6.5

Table 3: Thyroid Abnormalities

Thyroid Abnormality	Number of Patients (%)
Euthyroid	44 (55%)
Hypothyroidism (Subclinical)	14 (17.5%)
Hypothyroidism (Overt)	8 (10%)
Hyperthyroidism (Subclinical)	10 (12.5%)
Hyperthyroidism (Overt)	4 (5%)

A significant association was found between thyroid dysfunction and the severity of liver disease as measured by the Child-Pugh score (Table 4).

Table 4: Association Between Thyroid Function and Liver Disease Severity

Child-Pugh Score	Euthyroid	Hypothyroid	Hyperthyroid	p-value
A	16 (80%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	<0.001
B	18 (52.9%)	8 (23.5%)	8 (23.5%)	
C	10 (38.5%)	12 (46.2%)	6 (15.4%)	

Discussion

The demographic information showed that participants were mostly male (67.5%), with an average age of 52.4 years. Viral hepatitis (32.5%) and alcoholic liver disease (42.5%) were the two main causes of liver disease. According to the study, 45% of patients had thyroid dysfunction, including overt and subclinical hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism. The remaining 55% of patients were found to be euthyroid.

The correlation between the severity of liver disease and thyroid malfunction was a noteworthy discovery. Thyroid abnormalities were more common in patients with more severe liver disease (Child-Pugh grades B and C). To be more precise, only 38.5% of patients with a Child-Pugh score of C were euthyroid, compared to 80% of patients with an A score. This implies that the risk of thyroid dysfunction rises with the severity of liver illness.

These results underscore the importance of monitoring thyroid function in patients with chronic liver disease, particularly those with advanced disease. The high prevalence of thyroid abnormalities in this population indicates that thyroid dysfunction is a common comorbidity that could potentially impact the management and prognosis of liver disease. Regular thyroid function tests could help in early detection and treatment of thyroid disorders, thereby improving the overall clinical outcomes for these patients.

Overall, the study shows that thyroid dysfunction is significantly more common in patients with chronic liver illness and that there is a direct correlation between the severity of liver disease and thyroid abnormalities. According to this research, individuals with chronic liver disease should receive comprehensive treatment that includes routine thyroid monitoring and management. This is known as integrated care. It is necessary to do additional study to investigate the underlying

causes and create focused therapies to manage thyroid dysfunction in this susceptible population.

In a tertiary hospital, a study assessed the relationship between thyroid function and chronic liver disease. 88 patients with liver cirrhosis or chronic liver disease and 88 healthy controls participated in the study. Results compared to controls indicated that individuals with chronic liver illness had significantly higher levels of abnormalities in thyroid function tests (free T3, free T4, and TSH). The degree of thyroid dysfunction, namely low levels of free T3 and free T4, was substantially correlated with the severity of liver damage as measured by the Child-Pugh score [5].

At a Goan tertiary care hospital, a cross-sectional study on thyroid dysfunction was carried out in 100 patients who had liver cirrhosis. Patients with liver cirrhosis had considerably lower mean levels of total T4 and free T3, according to the study. Reduced free T3 levels were substantially correlated with the severity of liver illness as determined by the Child-Pugh score. The mean TSH, total T3, and free T4 levels varied within Child-Pugh classes, but these differences were not statistically significant [6].

52 individuals with chronic liver disease in a tertiary care hospital participated in a study that evaluated thyroid function. Thirty-six percent of these patients had thyroid dysfunction, according to the study. The degree of liver illness and TSH levels showed a strong positive link, while T3 and T4 levels showed an inverse relationship. The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction was higher in hepatic encephalopathy patients [7].

50 patients with liver cirrhosis who were hospitalised to a tertiary care hospital in Bengaluru were examined for thyroid dysfunction. According to the study, 34% of the patients had high TSH levels. Hypothyroidism has been linked to a number of abnormal liver function tests as well as hepatic consequences, including portal

hypertension, hepatic encephalopathy, and jaundice [8].

Conclusion

This study emphasises how common thyroid dysfunction is in individuals with long-term liver illness, especially in the more severely affected patients. It is advised that these patients have regular thyroid function testing in order to quickly identify and treat any problems. The underlying processes and effects of thyroid dysfunction on the clinical outcomes of patients with chronic liver disease require further investigation.

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